
Comparative Study Of Library Automation Softwares: Slim21 And Koha

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Abstract:

Library automation software is very important aspect for library. Selection of right software for library and Information centers is a challenge for librarians. SLIM 21 and KOHA software are used in many libraries. Researcher compared both software considering all the aspects advantages, disadvantages, service providers, training facility, etc. This research paper will help to the librarian to select library automation software.

Keywords: Software, SLIM 21, KOHA.

Introduction:

Software package is the most crucial for the success of library automation as it has many implications for a library is operations services staff and users. The success of library automation depends largely on the selection of right software and its effective implementation. A wide variety of library software packages are available in the market. Selection of an appropriate package suited to a particular library and its intelligent implementation are challenging computer task in library automation process. Therefore libraries should evaluate and compare all the available software packages carefully in order to select the best one that can match both the priority requirements and available financial resources.

Need of the Study:

Today's Libraries are hybrid libraries. Resources are available in print format and digital format to provide quality services to the user's efficient administration of the library. Automation of the library is very essential. Library software the main

part of the library automation, hence the selection of the library software is very important. SLIM21 software is available commercially. Some Open Source Software (OSS) packages are available on Internet. KOHA is Open Source Software for Library Information Management.

Objectives of the Study:

1. To Study the SLIM21 Library software.
2. To study the KOHA Library Software.
3. To study comparatively SLIM21 and KOHA Library Software's

Scope of the Study:

The topic of the research work reflects its scope is to determine and analysis true various dimensions of SLIM21 and KOHA users in Pune city. It may be desirable to explain have as to why only two software packages were selected for present study. Researcher is interested to study SLIM21 because many libraries in Pune city are using SLM21.KOHA is Open Source

Software (OSS) package, available freely but use of this software are less in Pune city.

Hypothesis:

1. Open Sources Software's (OSS) for library Management are available.
2. KOHA software users are less.
3. SLIM21 users are more than KOHA.

Methodology:

Comparative research is a logical extension of descriptive studies. While descriptive studies focus on a single object / entity/ sample / system, comparative once cover description of more than one. Here more than one similar systems or samples are compared based on predetermined parameters that are relevant to the objective / hypothesis. Comparative studies lead to better understanding of the object of the study.

Colleges and Institutions are using SLIM21 and KOHA Library Automation Software's:

Following chart shows the users of SLIM21 and KOHA open source Library automation software. There are five Colleges are using KOHA Open Source Software and nine colleges are using SLIM21 software.

Figure No.1

Who selected library software for your library?

Table No.1: Library Software Selection

Sr. No	Software Selection by	No. of Colleges
1	Library committee	08
2	Principal's Recommendation	02
3	Librarian	07
4	Any other	0

Table No. 1 gives the information about Library software selection, this table shows that more 57 % Colleges are selecting Library Software by the Library Committee., and 14.28 % Colleges are selecting Library Software by Principals recommendations and 50% Colleges are selecting Library software by the Librarian.

Figure No. 2: Library Software Selection

Is demonstration facility available?

Table No.2: Availability of demonstration of Library Software

Sr. No	Demonstration	No. of Libraries	Percentage
1	Yes	12	85.71 %
2	No	1	7.14%
3	Not mentioned	1	7.14%
Total		14	100

Above table shows that 12 (85.71 %) Librarians have got demonstration of Library software. Against that one (7.14%) Librarian didn't get the demonstration of library software, and one librarian (7.14%) not responded this question.

Figure No.3

Table No. 3: SLIM21 and KOHA Availability of Demonstration

Sr. No	Software	Libraries	Yes	No	Not Responded
1	SLIM21	09	100%	0%	0%
2	KOHA	5	60%	20%	20%
Total		14	85.71%	7.14%	7.14%

Above table describes nine (100%) Libraries demonstration is available in SLIM21 Library software. Against that out of five libraries only three (60%) Libraries have got demonstration in KOHA Library software.

Is library Software Company providing training to library professionals?

Table No. 4: Availability of Software Training facility

Sr. No	Software Training	No of Libraries	Percentage
1	Yes	9	64 %
2	No	5	36%
Total		14	100 %

Above table describes nine, (64 %) Librarians got software training against that five (36%) Librarians are not trained.

Figure No. 4: Availability of Software Training facility

Table No. 5: SLIM21 and KOHA availability of Training facility

Sr. No	Software	Libraries	Yes	No
1	SLIM21	09	88.88%	11.11%
2	KOHA	5	20%	80%
Total		14	64.28%	35.71%

Above table describes eight (88.88%) SLIM21 Librarians are trained and only one (11.11%) Librarian of SLIM21 software is not trained. On the other side only one (20%) KOHA Librarian is trained. And four (80%) KOHA Librarian is not trained.

Figure No. 5: SLIM21 and KOHA availability of Software Training facility

Are software manual / documentation provided by the company?

In the answer of the question, following information got by the Librarians of the concern Libraries.

Table No. 6: Availability of Software Manual

Sr. No	Software Manual	No. of Libraries	Percentage
1	Yes	11	78.57 %
2	No	3	21.43 %
Total		14	100%

Above table expresses, out of 14 colleges 11 (78.57%) colleges are getting software manual or documentation. And 3 (21.43 %) Colleges are not getting software manual or documentation.

Figure No. 6: Availability of Software Manual**Table No. 7: SLIM21 and KOHA Availability of Software manual**

Sr. No	Software	Libraries	Yes	No	Not Responded
1	SLIM21	09	100%	0	0
2	KOHA	5	60%	20%	20%
Total		14	85.71	7.14%	7.14%

Above table explains that SLIM21 Nine Librarians (100%) availability of software manual. Against that KOHA three (60%) Librarian's availability of software manual and one Librarian (20%) don't have software manual. also one Librarian not responded the question.

What about maintenance and support facility for Library software?

Table No. 8: Maintenance and support facility for Library software

Sr. No	Maintenance and Support	No. of Libraries	Percentage
1	Yes	12	85.72%
2	No	02	14.28%
Total		14	100%

Above table explains that twelve libraries (85.72%) are getting Maintenance and support facility for Library software. and two (14.28%) Libraries are not getting maintenance and support facility for Library software.

Table No. 9: SLIM21 and KOHA Maintenance and support facility

Sr. No	Software	Total Libraries	Yes	No	Not Responded
1	SLIM21	09	100%	0%	0%
2	KOHA	5	40%	40%	20%
Total		14	140%	40%	20%

Above table explains that SLIM21 Nine Librarians (100%) availability of maintenance and support facility for Library software. Against that KOHA three (60%) Librarian's availability of Maintenance and support facility for Library software and one Librarian (20%) don't have maintenance and support facility for Library software also one Librarian not responded the question.

Is your software having multi-script facility? Our Indian literature is available in multi-language.

Table No. 10: Availability of multi-language facility

Sr. No	Multilanguage	No. of Libraries	Percentage
1	Yes	13	92.85%
2	No	1	7.15%
Total		14	100%%

Above table explains that thirteen libraries (92.85%) are having multi-language facility in the Library Software. and one

(7.15%) Library doesn't having multi-language facility in the Library Software.

Table No. 11: SLIM and KOHA

Availability of Multi-Language facility

Sr. No	Software	Libraries	Yes	No	Total Percentage
1	SLIM21	09	100%	0%	100%
2	KOHA	5	80%	20%	100%
Total		14	92.85%	7.14%	100%

Above table explains that SLIM21 (100%) libraries are having multi-language facility in the Library Software. and KOHA (80%) Libraries having multi-language facility and (20%) Libraries don't multi-language facility the Library Software. Are software user group / Forum of software is available?

Table No. 12: Availability of User Group

Sr. No	Software User Group	No. of Libraries	Percentage
1	Yes	8	57.14%
2	No	4	28.57%
3	No Response	2	14.28%
Total		14	100%

Above table explains that eight (57.14%) libraries having user group for the Library Software. And four (28.57%) Library doesn't having user group for the Library Software. And two (14.28%) Librarian not responded this question.

Table No. 13: SLIM21 and KOHA availability of Software User Group

Sr. No	Software	Libraries	Yes	No	No Response	Total
1	SLIM21	09	44.44%	44.44%	11.11	100%
2	KOHA	5	80%	0%	20%	100%
Total		14	57.14%	28.57%	14.28%	100%

Above table explains that SLIM21 (44.44%) libraries are having user group for the Library Software. SLIM21 (44.44%) libraries don't having user group for the Library Software. and SLIM21 (11.11%)

libraries not responded this question. KOHA (80%) Libraries having user group and (20%) Libraries not responded this question.

Findings:

1. All academic Institutes / Colleges can save the money of parent organization by using KOHA open source software for Library and Information Management.
2. Library software's KOHA and SLIM21 demonstration is very essential for the implementation in Libraries.
3. Library Software training is very essential for the all Library staff.
4. Academic Institutions must organize regularly workshops, training programs on Library software packages.
5. If SLIM21 will be available on open source platform, it will be beneficial to all library professionals.
6. Government bodies like MHRD, UGC, NAAC, AICTE, NBA, DTE, must force to the Universities, Colleges and Institutions to implement the Open Source Software's especially in Libraries.
7. Library and information science education provider i.e. Colleges, Universities, Institutions should incorporate advanced software's in the syllabi.
8. Library Software selection Committee / Librarian should select the Library Software which is available free and advanced.
9. KOHA software consultancy companies should provide AMC.

Conclusion:

Software Companies are developing Library software packages for Library Automation; only few software companies are using advanced technology in Library software Package. KOHA is a very good library software package for all the libraries. SLIM21 is used by all types'

college Libraries. If we compare overall performance of SLIM21 and KOHA, KOHA is very good Software, and SLIM21 is satisfactory and good.

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